

Yogasūtra of Patañjali

By Aaron Michael Ullrey, University of Houston, University of Naropa

Entry tags: Religious Group, Text, Sanskrit literature, Magic, Yoga, Hinduism, indic religion

Yogasūtra, commonly referred to in the plural as the Yogasūtras is the pre-eminent text for meditative yoga in the past and is interpreted by many practitioners of Modern Postural Yoga (MPY) to be the sources for all later yoga practice. This text sets out the eight limbs (anga) of yoga, and one of the most important strands of MPY is called Asthanga (8-limbed) after this list of elements in the yogasutrasyama (abstinences, the don'ts), niyama (observances, prescriptions, preliminaries, the do's), asana (yoga posture, body position, seat), pranayama (breath control, breath exercise, mantra), pratyahara (withdrawal of the senses from the objects of the senses, isolating the essence of mind/soul), dharana (concentration of the mind, focusing on the nature of the mind), dhyana (meditation welling in the mind) and samadhi (absorption into the mind, the universe, the sense powers). That said, MPY really only focuses on asana practice, and to some degree pranayama, effectively limiting the so-called eight limbs to only one or two. The majority of the 195 sutras (verses) are about the nature of the should and the physical world, meditation techniques, a single verse on mantra that is also the single verse referring to a god (the Lord of Yoga), preliminary actions and activities, and a wide range of yoga powers (Siddhis) and herbal manipulations (aushadhi). This text was composed at the beginning of the common era drawing from earlier writing in the Upanishads and Vedas, considered Hindu, and the epic Mahabharata, containing a wide range of discourse on yoga. It also draws from varied early Mahayana Buddhist sources. The Bhagavad Gita, from the Mahabharata, is stated to be the greatest discourse on yoga, but it describes at least eight types of yoga, and only certain sections resemble what is found in the Yogasutras of Patanjali. The general religious philosophical background should be interpreted according to the ancient philosophical school called Samkhya. While this text is claimed to be inherently hindu, these days, there are many threads of influence and there are few characteristics of Hinduism today: no Hindu pantheon, no temples, no bhakti. 195 verses or sutra make up the texts. The sutras are pithy and require quite a bit of interpretation to make meaning from the verses. Its first statement on yoga states: yogascittavrittinirodha, "yoga is the cessation of the turnings of the mind", which has been interpreted and translated in remarkably varied and diverse ways.. The yoga sutras are usually encountered with a commentary that explains the grammar, provides additional arguments, and defines the terms in each verse. There are many commentaries, but arguably there are 5-10 that are ubiquitous. One of the first commentaries is by a man named Vyasa (who shares his name with a Vedic seer) though Vyasa could have been Patanjali himself, and this commentary was relatively soon after the yoga sutras were first composed. The yogasutras together with Vyasa's commentary is titled the Yogasutrabhasya, often just referred to as the Bhasya. Here I am only addressing the 195 verses of the Yogasutra, and I will try to avoid adding too much interpretation from the commentaries, all of which should be studied as unique voice in a tradition of interpreting these important verses. But what is yoga? Yoga is a tradition of experiments to perfect the mind and body. However, the definition of experiments, perfection, mind, and body will determine the those yoga practices and ideas.

Date Range: 100 BCE - 300 CE

Region: Greater Bengali Region

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, Nepal, Bangladesh, India

Eastern and Central South Asia including Bangladesh, Eastern Nepal, and the Indian states of Bihar, West Bengal, Odisha, Chattisgarh, and parts of

eastern Uttar Pradesh. Worship of Sitala takes place at a variety of locales, including small shrines at local landmarks (trees, rivers, borders of early settlements) outside villages and towns, as well as at temple sites within rural and urban settlements. The British presence in Calcutta (modern Kolkata) became a defining presence on Bengali identity in the colonial period when the East India Company bought the villages of Gobindapur, Kalikata, and Sutanuti in 1690 and went on to shape the larger geographic area.

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Bryant Edwin F and Patañjali Patañjali. 2009. *The Yoga Sūtras of Patañjali : A New Edition Translation and Commentary with Insights from the Traditional Commentators*. New York: North Point Press.
- Source 2: White David Gordon. 2014. *The Yoga Sutra of Patanjali : A Biography*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Source 3: Larson Gerald James Patañjali Patañjali Vyāsa Vyāsa and Vācaspatimiśra Vācaspatimiśra. 2018. *Classical Yoga Philosophy and the Legacy of Sāṃkhya : With Sanskrit Text and English Translation of Pātañjala Yogasūtra-S Vyāsa Bhāṣya and Tattvavaiśarādī of Vācaspatimiśra* First ed. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass.

Notes: There are three major common studies with translations and discussions of the translations and commentaries. Bryant includes his own commentary drawing on several commentaries. Larson sketches out the philosophical details. White sets out the history of the text in world culture, Indic culture, and pop culture.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.sacred-texts.com/hin/yogasutr.htm>
- Source 1 Description: An older English translation.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.arlingtoncenter.org/Sanskrit-English.pdf>
- Source 2 Description: Hardnaft's transliteration and translation.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.embodiedphilosophy.com/sutras-bryant/>
- Source 3 Description: An online course with Edwin Bryant

Notes: Another excellent digital resources is the Yogic Studies podcast with all its archived podcasts and courses. This webpage represents the cutting edge of yoga scholarship. <https://www.yogicstudies.com>

- Source 1 URL: https://www.academia.edu/43296388/Pātañjalayogaśāstra_Proofs_

– Source 1 Description: Philip Maas entry into Brill's Encyclopedia of Hinduism (2022)

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://sanskritdocuments.org/sites/athayoga/sutras.html>

– Source 1 Description: Transliteration, translation, commentary.

– Source 2 URL: <https://shlokam.org/yogasutra/>

– Source 2 Description: Verse by verse devanagari, transliteration, and basic translation without commentaries.

– Source 3 URL:

https://www.jainfoundation.in/JAINLIBRARY/books/Yoga_Aphorisms_of_Patanjali_011118_std.pdf

– Source 3 Description: English Translation by Prabhavananda and Isherwood. Very famous translations.

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

–with Ink

Notes: A wide range of manuscripts, usually with commentaries. Many were written, then sorta faded out, and then in the 19th and 20th century the text became the most pervasive in the discourse about yoga.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

–Specify: Various paper types and also, presumably, some mss on palm.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Notes: In the 20th century there have been temples built to review the sutras and their purported author.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Many versions with commentaries, but little variance in root text.

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Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– I don't know

Notes: Sectarian groups starting in the 15th century would have recruited new ascetics, but these groups were not that interested in this specific text. Nowadays there are yoga groups that recruit popularly, but only some of these groups connect to this text.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The text would not have been connected to a specific group per se. These days it is considered religious and the official religion is Modern Postural Yoga. Some Hindus now claim it as an essentiality religious or officially religious text.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: Different commentaries reinterpret the yogasutras according to sectarian and religious perspectives: hathayoga, bhakti, vedanta, Jainism.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Is it orally recited?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Was not originally recited. These days, however, the yogasutras are chanted in many yoga studios, often as a preliminary to practice.

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– No

Notes: General blessings

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– I don't know

Notes: Reveals practices which will lead to hidden knowledge through practice

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– No

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

–Specify: Rituals here are meditative practices that bring about some sort of perfection, whether that be for magi powers or liberation and meditative accomplishment. That said, modern asana practice and attending yoga studio classes should be also considered ritual.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– No

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– I don't know

Notes: The text does not describe any sort of real group practices. The yogi is singular, though he practices according to the teachings of a guru. Today, however, yoga can be individual, group, or even mass practices.

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– I don't know

Notes: Daily practice for yogis. MPY practitioners may practice daily.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

Notes: MPY has orthodoxy and orthopraxy by certain groups, but there is no clear governance or authority other than a general guru and the Lord of Yoga in the text.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

Notes: The text is clearly pulling from ascetic traditions and warrior traditions at the time. Commentaries have all sorts of different synchronism. MPY is broadly synchronous with physical cultures, new thought, and Indic practices.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: There are herbs used, but intoxication is not clearly the aim.

Is there material significance to the text?

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Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: Spirit or purush is operate from the sense objects. The mind is also considered to be a physical organ.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Notes: Completely distinct but confused with sensory objects

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally negative

Notes: When aiming toward yoga practices then the aggregates are negative, but just describing the world they are neither positive nor negative.

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

– Specify: Metaphysics and gnostic realization. Gnostic relization shows the world and aggregate to be negative for it confuses spirit with matter.

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: Based on Sankhya.....purusha (spirit) and prakriti (nature) are distinct, and liberation only comes from the operation.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– I don't know

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Notes: The text can be interpreted to isolate nature and the soul to bring about liberation. Or the souls may not be souls but only a single soul and realization realizes this. Or the goal of practice may be to unite soul with a god, though there is only a single verse on this.

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Notes: This text has all of the above. Lists of practices and preliminaries. Vocabulary definition of yoga and limbs. Ritual practices to gain magic powers are extensive.

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Notes: Ascetics would be celibate, but the text can be interpreted for householders. These days it is not a text interpreted with traditional celibacy.

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The yogi householder maintains social norms, though the yogi ascetic and renunciate would be counterculture.

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: New and modern versions may have illumination, but traditionally there were no diagrams or even depictions of poses and practices.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: There is not a specific lineage, though many groups will claim their group to be founded in the tradition stretching back to the yogasutras/

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The YS should be interpreted according to general Indic religion at the time in which there is physical death and rebirth but one also aspire to a heaven birth (which is temporary) or to a rebirth in the realm of yogis and heroes.

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Monogamy (males)

– No

Monogamy (females)

– Yes

Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

Notes: In time, sexuality is thought to be descriptive to yoga.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: The root text is the same, with little philological difference, but the commentaries and translations are wildly divergent.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– Yes

Notes: All sources like this with commentaries will debate which is the greatest version. Generally that point of the author is established as the best, and all the prior versions will be summarized and judged.

↳ Age of extant version of text?
– Yes

↳ Content of text?
– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?
– Yes

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

↳ In human form?
– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form?
– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?
– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?
– Yes

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?
– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?
– I don't know

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– Yes

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions?

– Specify: Liberation as born to be with god, in Bhakti, or reborn as a yogi in the next life, or heaven.....there is a wide range.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: The rewards come through proper practices.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - Yes
 - Notes: Strength is to support meditation.

- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - I don't know
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - I don't know
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
 - Yes

Notes: Lots of preliminaries on body cleansing and practice methods.

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: Fasting is prescribed for specific practices and goals. Also varied dietary regulations are included.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– I don't know

Notes: It is not a revealed sources, like the vedas. It is considered a written or remembered (smrti) text. It is recited now, and in recent times folk have started revering Patanjali, the author, to be a divine or mythological figure.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: Food should be considered pure and non stimulating.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: No.....but Yogis in India in general are usually buried as opposed to cremated.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– Yes

Notes: Some there are physical positions, and these days in MPY a lot looks painful and uncomfortable. That said, the single verse in the text states that the body positions should be made firm (drdha) and comfortable (sukha).

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Notes: There is a god who is the Lord of Yoga (Yogeshwar), but only in one verse and he is not described, just stated to be associated with the syllable Om. One can, through yogic vision, see all sorts of gods and dieties.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: There is a vague sense that there are previously liberated yogis or perfected yogis, but there is little real description of them.

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: Traditions of yogic suicide are found later in the tantra yoga perspective.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: While there is little in the text, in particular, this text exists in an embodied world of spirits and deities and planets and forces.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text does give instructions for making contact with forces and beings, but the details of that communication are not clear.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– Yes

Notes: The demons of this war should always be considered hungry, not evil or malicious but hungry.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Notes: If the yogi leaves his life, then he leaves all the goods and valuables from his prior life.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Regular physical and meditative practice.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– I don't know

Notes: Only one description of the lord of yoga, but generally there would have been a pantheon of deities forming the background and context.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: Siddhas are once human who were perfected.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: I would argue that all these practices require some risk, hoping to transform the self.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: One verse on lord of yoga.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: There are a wide range of preliminaries and practices.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Incomprehensible?

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: A yogi can learn things using yoga-visions and maybe see at a distance or into the future or past, but it is not divination as in a divination ritual.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Notes: Presumably the student might practice with the guru, but the whole text describes meditative and physical rituals that are these experiments with perfecting the mind and body.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: No particular sacred geography or connection to places.

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

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Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: There is not a specific lineage, though many groups will claim their group to be founded in the tradition stretching back to the yogasutras/

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: Spirit or purush is operate from the sense objects. The mind is also considered to be a physical organ.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Notes: Completely distinct but confused with sensory objects

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally negative

Notes: When aiming toward yoga practices then the aggregates are negative, but just describing the world they are neither positive nor negative.

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

– Specify: Metaphysics and gnostic realization. Gnostic relization shows the world and aggregate to be negative for it confuses spirit with matter.

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: Based on Sankhya.....purusha (spirit) and prakriti (nature) are distinct, and liberation only comes from the operation.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– I don't know

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Notes: The text can be interpreted to isolate nature and the soul to bring about liberation. Or the souls may not be souls but only a single soul and realization realizes this. Or the goal of practice may be to unite soul with a god, though there is only a single verse on this.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The YS should be interpreted according to general Indic religion at the time in which there is physical death and rebirth but one also aspire to a heaven birth (which is temporary) or to a rebirth in the realm of yogis and heroes.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

↳ In human form?

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form?

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– Yes

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– I don't know

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– Yes

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions?

– Specify: Liberation as born to be with god, in Bhakti, or reborn as a yogi in the next life, or heaven.....there is a wide range.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: No.....but Yogis in India in general are usually buried as opposed to cremated.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Notes: There is a god who is the Lord of Yoga (Yogeshwar), but only in one verse and he is not described, just stated to be associated with the syllable Om. One can, through yogic vision, see all sorts of gods and dieties.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: There is a vague sense that there are previously liberated yogis or perfected yogis, but there is little real description of them.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: While there is little in the text, in particular, this text exists in an embodied world of spirits and deities and planets and forces.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text does give instructions for making contact with forces and beings, but the details of that communication are not clear.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: The demons of this war should always be considered hungry, not evil or malicious but hungry.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– I don't know

Notes: Only one description of the lord of yoga, but generally there would have been a pantheon of deities forming the background and context.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: Siddhas are once human who were perfected.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: One verse on lord of yoga.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Incomprehensible?

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: A yogi can learn things using yoga-visions and maybe see at a distance or into the future or past, but it is not divination as in a divination ritual.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: The rewards come through proper practices.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The yogi householder maintains social norms, though the yogi ascetic and renunciate would be counterculture.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - Yes
 - Notes: Strength is to support meditation.
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - I don't know
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No

↳ Optimism/hope
– I don't know

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes

Notes: Lots of preliminaries on body cleansing and practice methods.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Notes: Ascetics would be celibate, but the text can be interpreted for householders. These days it is not a text interpreted with traditional celibacy.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)
– No

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

Notes: In time, sexuality is thought to be descriptive to yoga.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: Fasting is prescribed for specific practices and goals. Also varied dietary regulations are included.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: Food should be considered pure and non stimulating.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– Yes

Notes: Some there are physical positions, and these days in MPY a lot looks painful and uncomfortable. That said, the single verse in the text states that the body positions should be made firm (drdha) and comfortable (sukha).

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: Traditions of yogic suicide are found later in the tantra yoga perspective.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Notes: If the yogi leaves his life, then he leaves all the goods and valuables from his prior life.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Regular physical and meditative practice.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: I would argue that all these practices require some risk, hoping to transform the self.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: There are a wide range of preliminaries and practices.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Notes: Presumably the student might practice with the guru, but the whole text describes meditative and physical rituals that are these experiments with perfecting the mind and body.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: No particular sacred geography or connection to places.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: In later times the powers of yogis were thought to make them fine warriors and mercenaries.

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A band

Notes: There are groups associated with a guru.

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Notes: Informal teaching relationships.

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Notes: There are no real charitable or social organization in the text.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Spiritual Elect

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– I don't know

Notes: The text may have been limited in some of its uses and interpretations later, but no real restriction in the text here.

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Notes: Presumably the main audience would be yogis, but they could be denunciates or they could be householders.

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: This is a text that does not describe gender specifically, but the perspective and audience would have been almost entirely male.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– I don't know

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The guru is revered.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– I don't know

Notes: Performing the practices will give power and super power

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

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Bureaucracy

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Public Works

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Taxation

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– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: In later times the powers of yogis were thought to make them fine warriors and mercenaries.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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